

DNA AMPLIFICATION FOR METABARCODING

This setup is for sequencing on the MiSeq/Novaseq with 12s primers using AmpliTag Gold MasterMix.

- 1) If you have extracted your samples in the eDNA Extraction lab, you bring your aliquots with you in two bags into the PCR-setup lab. Bring also your suit from the extraction lab.
- 2) Throw away the outer bag and clean with bleach the inner bag around your samples.
- 3) Put your samples in the fridge while you clean the hoods and equipment following the protocol.
- 4) Take necessary chemicals out of the freezer 30 mins prior to work to defrost. This takes approx. the same time as UV'ing the hood after cleaning, so do this simultaneously.
- 5) The PCR-mix is as follows:

REAGENT	VOLUME (μL)
AmpliTag Gold Master Mix	10.00
Bovine serum albumin (BSA)	0.16
H ₂ O	4.84
Primers Mix (F + R)	2.0
DNA template	3.0

- 6) Prepare the MasterMix for your samples in triplicates:

MASTERMIX	X1, μL	X8, μL	X100, μL (96-WELL PLATE)	X?, μL
AmpliTag Gold	3x10 = 30	240	3,000	
BSA	3x0.16 = 0.48	3.84	48	
H ₂ O	3x4.84 = 14.52	116.16	1452	

(Use the space in the last column to do your calculation dependent on sample number).

- 7) Give the MasterMix a thorough vortex and spin it down.
- 8) Spin down the plate with primers.
- 9) Add 15.0 μl to each well that will be used in the PCR.
- 10) Add 2 μl of the primer mix to each well.
- 11) Move to the other hood before adding 3 μl of the DNA template to each well with MasterMix. (If your samples are in the Genetic lab B310, you add the 3 μl of DNA in the Metabarcoding Workstation in B310).
- 12) Seal, wrap in bags, put in fridge while you clean the hoods following the cleaning protocol.